

Laser Frequency combs as calibrators for Astronomy

The quest for precision

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The quest for ultimate RV precision

2005: Nobel prize to T. Hänsch and J. Hall for their work on laser precision spectroscopy and the LFC

2007-2011: “demonstrator program” on HARPS

2012-ongoing: testing and commissioning a LFC for routine operation on HARPS

The quest for ultimate RV precision

	HARPS	ESPRESSO	HIRES (Phase A)
RV precision	1 m/s	10 cm/s	2 cm/s
Distance on CCD	17 nm	16 Å	3.2 Å

Silicon lattice constant: 5.4 Å

Limitation of traditional calibrators

- ThAr (hollow cathode lamps):
 - Low line density
 - Blending
 - High dynamics
 - 20cm/s – 30cm/s scatter
 - Uncertainty on the line positions (20-80m/s)

- Iodine absorption cells:
 - Reduced throughput
 - High dynamics
 - Limited wavelength coverage (~ 500nm – 650nm)
 - Spectral information “destroyed” by the I₂ forest

Limitation of traditional calibrators

Figure 14
Float-line

The ideal calibrator

- ✧ As many as possible, non-blended, equally spaced lines
(line spacing tuned to the resolution of the spectrograph)
- ✧ Smooth intensity distribution across the spectrum
- ✧ Unresolved lines
- ✧ Extreme stability (better than $2 \cdot 10^{-11}$)

Laser Frequency Comb: basic equation

$$\omega_n = n\omega_r + \omega_{CE}$$

ω_r and ω_{CE} locked to an atomic clock and tunable

$n =$ large integer ($n \sim 10^6$)

atomic clock = micro-wave regime

Laser Frequency combs:

- Satisfy all requirements of our “ideal calibrator”
- Mostly used for metrology, laser spectroscopy
- Commercially available

Need to adapt the commercial product to the specific needs of an astronomical spectrograph

From the off-the-shelf LFC to the Astro-comb

Off the shelf LFC:

- Repetition frequency: 250MHz
- Central wavelength: $\sim 1060\text{nm}$ (Yb fiber laser)
- Pulse width: $\sim 100\text{fs}$ \Rightarrow wavelength coverage $\sim 40\text{nm}$

Astro-comb (for HARPS):

- Repetition frequency: $\sim 18\text{GHz}$
- Central wavelength: 530nm
- Wavelength coverage: $> 200\text{nm}$

From the off-the-shelf LFC to the Astro-comb

- Filtering via Fabry-Perot cavities
- Spectral broadening via non linear processes in a Photonic Crystal Fiber (PCF)
- Coupling to the spectrograph

The HARPS Astro-comb - 2015

Probst R. et al. SPIE 2016

The 2009 HARPS Astro-comb

The 2015 HARPS Astro-comb

Fabry-Perot cavities (HARPS)

- Filtering factor: 72
- Finesse (FSR/FWHM) ~ 2000
- Temperature compensated (closed loop)
- Need to suppress by at least 50dB the unwanted modes
- Three FPC used in series for better suppression

Spectral broadening (HARPS)

The natural coverage of the LFC is $\lambda^2/(100\text{fs})/c \sim 40\text{nm}$

We request at least 200nm (we got 180nm so far)

Broadening is performed via highly non-linear processes in the PCF (Photonic Crystal Fiber):

four wave mixing: 3 photons \rightarrow 1 photon: $\omega_{\text{out}} = \omega_1 \pm \omega_2 \pm \omega_3$

Challenges:

- Need high power
- Amplify modes suppressed by the FPC
- Output is not “deterministic”
- Reliability / lifetime

Spectral broadening

Life time of the PCF

Trade off life-time vs. wavelength coverage
<900 hours for a 510nm-760nm WL coverage

Modes Scrambling

No scrambl. Scrambl. Scrambl. + squeeze (G. Avila)

Dynamic scrambling is essential

Modes Scrambling

- Couple from the single mode PCF to a multimode fiber
- Destroy temporal coherence => dynamic scrambling
- Fill as many as possible spatial modes => static scrambling

The CCD geometry

Clear detection of the CCD stitching pattern every 512 pixels

Wilken, T. et al.: MNRAS, 2010

Stability

Wilken, T. et al., Nature, 2012

Stability

$$\sigma_y^2(\tau) = \frac{1}{2} \langle (\bar{y}_{n+1} - \bar{y}_n)^2 \rangle$$

Noise in the LFC data is
Statistical down to
1 cm/s !!!

Probst, R. et al., SPIE, 2016

Study of line profiles variations via LFC

The line profile depends on the line position on the detector (the figure shows the third moment γ across the chip)

Fei Zaho et al., poster at XXVIII IAU-GA

Study of line profiles variations via LFC

The asymmetry of the lines depends on the line intensity and varies differently on the two sides of the detector. a hint that effects such as Charge Transfer Efficiency might be at play.

Fei Zaho et al., poster at XXVIII IAU-GA

Study of line profiles variations via LFC

- Changing the repetition frequency changes the mode spacing
- “Scan” the detector and characterize it pixel by pixel
- Build a database of PSF as function of position in the detector
- Include in calibration plan

Background (see D. Milakovic poster)

- Likely due to ASE (Amplified Spontaneous Emission)
- Increases with amplifiers current
- Increases with degradation of FP coatings
- Polarization dependent

Trade-off: PCF lifetime is also polarization dependent (better in the “other” polarization)

LFC on sky – Stellar RVs (work in progress)

Star	N	δRV (m/s) (ThAr-LFC)	STD(δRV) (m/s)	RV_err	LFC Calib. stability (cm/s)	SNR @ 550nm	T (K)	FWHM (km/s)
HD330075	4	-31.11	0.54	1.72	12 \pm 3	65	6295	6.82
HD75289	8	-30.43	0.30	0.77	12 \pm 3	214	6120	8.60
HD76700	4	-31.53	0.30	1.04	12 \pm 3	100	5726	7.27
HD85512	5	-35.43	0.39	1.31	14 \pm 3	128	4715	6.04

- Offset ThAr – LFC calibration (expected)
- Calibration stability limited to the 12cm/s photon noise of the LFC

Work in progress !

Long term measurements

Still work to do on the LFC injection & scrambling

Photon noise

$$\delta RV = \frac{c}{Q \cdot \sqrt{N_{e^-}}} \propto \frac{1}{SNR}$$

S/N ~ 100 => RV ~ 100cm/s

S/N ~ 1000 => RV ~ 10cm/s

S/N ~ 10000 => RV ~ 1cm/s

ESPRESSO

HIRES

LFC in La Silla

HARPS
NIRPS ??

LFC in Paranal

- Rocky planets
- Fundamental constants
- 10cm/s RV precision

LFC in Armazones

HIRES

Flagship science drivers include:

- Exo-planets characterization
- Galactic archaeology
- AGN
- Fundamental constants
- Sandage test
- IGM

~ 2cm/s RV precision !!

Conclusions

- ❑ Laser frequency combs for calibrating astronomical spectrographs are becoming a reality
- ❑ A LFC has been tested on HARPS demonstrating a stability better than 1 cm/s
- ❑ Special care has to be taken on LFC light injection into the spectrograph
- ❑ LFC shall be used to calibrate geometrical non-homogeneity of detectors
- ❑ Detector effects such as non-linearity or CTE are important
- ❑ Line profile variations as function of location and intensity levels must be taken into account for proper data reduction
- ❑ Still open issues with wavelength coverage and life time of a critical component